

The Effects of Interactive-Engagement and Analogy-Enhanced Instructional Strategies On Secondary School Students' Self-Efficacy in Chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria

AUTHOR(S): Amos Olusola OGUNJOBI (Ph.D),
AND
Stella Kemilola EKUNDAYO (Ph.D)

Abstract

The study investigated the effects of interactive-engagement and analogy-enhanced instructional strategies on secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study adopted a pre-test post-test control group quasi-experimental design. The population for the study consisted of all the 5,046 senior secondary school II students offering Chemistry in all the 187 public senior secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria as at the time of the study. The sample for the study consisted of all the 198 SSS II students offering Chemistry found in intact classes of the six secondary schools selected for the study using multistage sampling procedure. Students' Self-Efficacy Rating Scale (SSERS) was used for data collection and validity was established by experts in the field of science education and psychology. Test re-test method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded coefficient of 0.86. The research question raised was answered using descriptive statistics while the postulated hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics involving Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the result revealed that there was significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional instructional strategies in Chemistry while the self-efficacy of students exposed to Interactive-Engagement, Analogy-Enhanced and conventional strategies of teaching do not differ by

IJARBAS

Accepted 20 June 2021
Published 25 June 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5072351

gender and school location. It was recommended among others that Chemistry teachers should embrace innovative instructional strategies by deliberate use of interactive-engagement and analogy-enhanced instructional strategies in the learning process in order to facilitate better self-efficacy in Chemistry.

Keywords: Interactive-Engagement, Analogy-Enhanced, Self-Efficacy, Chemistry,

About Author

Author(s):

Amos Olusola OGUNJOBI (Ph.D.)
Science Education Department
Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria
olusola.ogunjobi@fuoye.edu.ng

And

Stella Kemilola EKUNDAYO (Ph.D.)
Science Education Department
Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria
stella.ekundayo@fuoye.edu.ng

Introduction

Chemistry is a versatile science subject that deals with the composition, properties and uses of matter. Chemistry is the scientific study of interaction of chemical substances that constitute atoms of the subatomic particles; protons, electrons and neutrons. It is an integral part of the science curriculum both at the senior secondary school as well as higher institutions. One of the objectives of science education is to develop students' interest towards science and technology. Teachers are therefore expected to devise ways of motivating their students to develop positive attitudes towards science and science related disciplines (Adeyemo, 2012).

Self-efficacy is the perception of students about their own ability to perform well. Navarro and Santos (2013) defined self-efficacy as an impression that one is capable of performing in a certain manner or certain goals. They further defined it as one's belief in his/her capacity to perform a specific action successfully. Findings from various researches had shown that self-efficacy predicts students' performance both directly and indirectly across academic areas and levels (Pajares & Urdan, 2006; Usher & Pajares, 2005). Apart from being an indicator of academic performance, self-efficacy has been reported to be associated with resilience, motivation and goal orientation which are predictors of success in school work (Britner and Pajares, 2006).

Self-efficacy determines how people feel, think, motivate themselves and behave. Such beliefs produce these diverse effects through five major processes, which include cognitive, motivational, affective and selection processes. A strong sense of efficacy enhances human accomplishment and personal well-being in many ways such as academic achievement. Students might have different self-efficacy judgements in different types of task or domains. For instance, a student who has high self-efficacy in Biology might not be so efficacious in Chemistry. Self-efficacy influences people's choice of tasks, showing efforts and persistence at the task. No wonder, Britner (2008) submitted that it is a better predictor of performance and motivation when compared to other variables and that efficacious students look for new challenges, show persistence at tasks and have the ultimate success. Similarly, Kiran and Sungur (2011) have affirmed the relationship between self-efficacy and students' performance.

Ineffective teaching strategies lower students' self-efficacy and consequently, affect their performance negatively. Hence there is need for further research into some new teaching strategies that would enhance self-efficacy, improve academic performance, and at the same time, be simple enough for easy conveyance of instructions.

Several studies have been carried out to investigate the efficacy of new teaching strategies in Chemistry. Some of these strategies include among others; game-based learning strategies, concept mapping/problem solving strategies and the use of analogy in pictorial representation. However, observation revealed that not much has been done on interactive-engagement and analogy-enhanced instructional strategies.

The interactive-engagement instructional strategy is designed to promote conceptual understanding through minds-on and sometimes hands-on-activities which yield immediate feedback through discussion with peers and instructors. The study of Cahyadi (2007) indicated that an interactive approach to teaching has a number of positive effects on students' motivation and learning. He further observed that instructional model where students participate in the process of investigation and discoveries by interacting with one another and with the teaching and learning materials, have been shown to improve students' fundamental understanding in Chemistry.

The other strategy been used in this study is analogy-enhanced instructional strategy. Analogy enhanced instructional strategy adopts the concept of storytelling into teaching which according to Genden (2011), creates interest and reduce anxiety. This instructional strategy uses the concepts that students are familiar with to provide an analogical bridge to an unfamiliar concept thus motivating and provoking the interest of students (Orgil & Thomas, 2007). Samara (2013) defined analogy as a strategy that helps students form initial mental models of key science concept by facilitating introduction of concepts in ways that are concrete, meaningful and relevant to the students. According to Duniya (2009) an analogy is a comparison of something unfamiliar with something familiar in order to explain a shared principle; for example, when a teacher wants a student to learn from what he/she already knows. An analogy is built on the framework of the learners' existing knowledge so they are not starting from scratch.

Many studies have shown that analogues-enhanced instructional strategy causes a better acquisition of scientific concepts than the conventional instructional strategy and help students to integrate knowledge more effectively (Aybuke & Omen, 2012). For the use of analogies to be effective, teachers need to prepare these analogues in details and make sure that there are comprehensible connection between the analogues and the targets they represent. It is against this background, therefore, that this study is poised to investigate the effects of interactive-engagement and analogy-enhanced instructional strategies on the self-efficacy of secondary school students in Chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effects of interactive-engagement and analogy-enhanced instructional strategies on secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

1. secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry before and after treatment;
2. the difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional instructional strategies in chemistry;
3. the difference in the self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional strategies in chemistry; and
4. the difference in the self-efficacy of rural and urban students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional strategies in chemistry.

Research Question

This research question was raised for the study:

1. What is secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry before and after treatment?

Research Hypotheses

These hypotheses were postulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional instructional strategies in chemistry.
2. There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional strategies in chemistry.
3. There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of rural and urban students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional strategies in chemistry.

Methodology

The study adopted a pre-test post-test control group quasi- experimental design. The population for the study consisted of all the 5,046 senior secondary school II students offering Chemistry in all the 187 public senior secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria as at the time of the study. The sample for the study consisted of all the 198 SSS II students offering Chemistry found in intact classes of the six secondary schools selected for the study using multistage sampling procedure.

Students' Self-Efficacy Rating Scale (SSERS) was used for data collection in the study. The validity of SSERS was established by experts in the field of science education and psychology while necessary corrections arising from their observations were effected in making the final draft of the instruments. To determine the reliability of the instrument, test re-test method was used, which yielded coefficient of 0.86 for SSERS. Hence, the instrument was adjudged to be consistent, stable and reliable enough for use. The research question raised was answered using descriptive statistics involving mean and standard deviation while the postulated hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics involving Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) and Scheffe Post-hoc analysis were applied where necessary.

Results

Research Question 1: What is secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry before and after treatment?

In order to answer the question, mean scores of secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry before and after treatment were computed and compared. The result is presented in Table 2

Table 1: Secondary Schools Students' Self-Efficacy in Chemistry Before and After Treatment.

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Difference	% Mean Difference	Ranking
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Interactive Engagement	62	43.71	4.61	64.00	3.05	20.29	31.70	2 nd
Analogy-Enhanced	72	42.99	5.61	69.67	4.30	26.68	38.30	1 st
Conventional	64	42.08	4.11	47.55	4.25	5.47	11.50	3 rd
Total	198	42.92	4.87	60.74	10.21	17.82	16.80	

Table 1 reveals that students in the Interactive-Engagement group had a mean score of 43.71 on self-efficacy in Chemistry while those in the Analogy-Enhanced and conventional groups were 42.99 and 42.08 respectively before treatment. On exposure to treatment, students in the Analogy-Enhanced group had the highest mean score of 69.67, closely

followed by those exposed to Interactive Engagement (mean=64.00) while students exposed to conventional method had the least post-test mean score of 47.55. This implies that the secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry before treatment was low but increased on exposure to treatment. The secondary school students' self-efficacy in Chemistry before and after treatment is further depicted in Figure i.

Figure i: Bar Chart Showing Secondary Schools Students' Self-Efficacy in Chemistry Before and After Treatment.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of students using interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional instructional strategy in Chemistry.

Post-test mean scores of students' self-efficacy using interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional instructional strategy were computed and subsequently compared for statistical significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 2

Table 2: ANCOVA Showing Students' Self-Efficacy by Treatment

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Corrected Model	17558.742	3	5852.914	379.612	.000
Covariate (Pretest)	22.737	1	22.737	1.475	.226
Group	17484.308	2	8742.154	567.004	.000
Error	2991.122	194	15.418		

Total	751099.000	198			
Corrected Total	20549.864	197			

$p < 0.05$

Table 2 shows that there is significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students' self-efficacy using interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced and the conventional instructional strategy ($F_{2, 194} = 567.004$, $p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is rejected.

Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) was used to determine the effectiveness of treatment (Instructional strategy) at enhancing students' self-efficacy in Chemistry. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) of Students' Self-Efficacy in Chemistry by Treatment

Grand mean=60.74					
Variable + Category	N	Unadjusted Devn'	Eta ²	Adjusted For Independent + Covariate	Beta
Interactive-Engagement	62	3.26	.85	3.16	.06
Analogy-Enhanced	72	8.93		8.92	
Conventional	64	-13.19		-12.74	
Multiple R					0.060
Multiple R ²					0.004

Table 3 reveals that, with a grand mean of 60.74, students exposed to Analogy-Enhanced had the highest adjusted mean score of 69.66 ($60.74 + 8.92$) on self-efficacy in Chemistry, closely followed by those taught with Interactive-Engagement instructional strategy with an adjusted mean score of 63.90 ($60.74 + 3.16$) while students in the conventional group had the least adjusted mean score of 48.00 ($60.74 + (-12.74)$). This implies that Interactive-Engagement and Analogy-Enhanced are effective instructional strategies for enhancing students' self-efficacy in Chemistry. The treatment accounted for about 85% ($Eta^2 = 0.85$) of the observed variance in students' self-efficacy in Chemistry. However about 15% of the observed variance in students' self-efficacy is not accounted for during treatment, because they are believed to be on the other hidden variables not checked in this study. Hence there is need for post-hoc analysis. In this case, Scheffe Post-hoc Test was carried out

In order to locate the sources of pairwise significant difference among the groups, Scheffe post-hoc test was carried out. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Scheffe Post-Hoc Analysis of Students' Self-Efficacy in Chemistry by Treatment

Group	1	2	3	N	Mean
Interactive Engagement (1)		*	*	62	64.00
Analogy- Enhanced (2)			*	72	69.67

Conventional Method (3)				64	47.55
-------------------------	--	--	--	----	-------

p<0.05 * denotes pair of group significance

Table 4 reveals that there is significant difference between the self-efficacy of students exposed to interactive Engagement and Analogy-Enhanced instructional strategy at 0.05 level of significance. Similarly, the mean difference between the self-efficacy of students in Interactive Engagement and control, Analogy-Enhanced and control groups is statistically significant at 0.05 level in each case.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced strategies and the conventional method in Chemistry.

The mean scores of male and female students exposed to the interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced strategies (experimental groups) and the conventional method (control group) in Chemistry in the students' Self-Efficacy Rating Scale were computed and subsequently compared for statistical significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: 2 x 3 ANCOVA Showing Students' Self-Efficacy in Chemistry by Gender and Treatment

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Corrected Model	17662.319	6	2943.720	194.716	.000
Covariate(Pretest)	21.452	1	21.452	1.419	.235
Sex	31.708	1	31.708	2.097	.149
Group	15187.556	2	7593.778	502.299	.000
Sex * Group	64.609	2	32.304	2.137	.121
Error	2887.545	191	15.118		
Total	751099.000	198			
Corrected Total	20549.864	197			

p>0.05 * denotes interactive effects of sex on the group

Table 5 shows that there is no significant difference in the self-efficacy of male and female students using interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced strategies and conventional method in Chemistry at 0.05 level of significance ($F_{2, 191} = 2.137$; $p > 0.05$). The null hypothesis is not rejected. Similarly, the main effect of sex ($F_{1, 191} = 2.097$, $p > 0.05$) on students' self-

efficacy in Chemistry is not statistically significant at 0.05 level. However, treatment had significant effect on students' self- efficacy in Chemistry ($F_{2,191}= 502.299$, $p<0.05$).

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in self-efficacy of rural and urban students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced strategies and the conventional method in Chemistry.

Self-efficacy mean scores of students in Chemistry exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced strategies and the conventional strategy in urban areas and rural areas were computed and subsequently compared for statistical significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: ANCOVA Showing Students' Self-Efficacy in School Location by treatment

Source	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Corrected Model	17626.907	6	2937.818	191.971	.000
Covariate(Pre-test)	28.071	1	28.071	1.834	.177
Location	4.694	1	4.694	.307	.580
Group	9562.475	2	4781.238	312.429	.000
Location * Group	68.068	2	34.034	2.224	.111
Error	2922.957	191	15.303		
Total	751099.000	198			
Corrected Total	20549.864	197			

$p>0.05$ * denotes interactive effects of location on the group

Table 6 shows that there is no significant difference in the self-efficacy mean scores of rural and urban students exposed to interactive-engagement, analogy-enhanced strategies and the conventional strategy in Chemistry at 0.05 level of significance ($F_{2,191}= 2.224$; $p>0.05$). The null hypothesis is not rejected. Also, the main effect school location on students' self-efficacy in Chemistry is not significant at 0.05 level ($F_{1,191}= 0.307$; $p>0.05$). However, treatment had significant effect on students' self-efficacy in Chemistry ($F_{2,191}= 312.238$; $p<0.05$).

Discussion

The study revealed that the students' self-efficacy in chemistry before treatment was very low but improved tremendously after treatment. By implication, therefore the treatment has effect in improving the self-efficacy of students in chemistry. The study also showed there was significant difference in the self-efficacy of students using interactive-engagement, analogy enhanced and the conventional strategies. This result is in tandem with the work of Cheung (2015) who opined that individuals who possess a high degree of self-efficacy are more likely to attempt challenging tasks, persist longer at them, and exert more effort in the process. When the students master a challenging task with limited assistance, their level of self-efficacy beliefs affects how they approach new challenges and contributes well to their performance since these beliefs have been established to influence thought processes, motivation, and behaviour.

Self-efficacy is characterized by self-regulation especially in the use of effective instructional strategies. Britner (2008) also submitted that efficacious students look for new challenges, show persistence at tasks and have the ultimate success. This is also affirmed by the study of Kiran and Sungur (2011) which affirmed the relationship between self-efficacy and students' performance.

Another finding of this study showed that there was no significant difference between the self-efficacy of male and female students exposed to the two strategies and the conventional method in Chemistry. This finding contradicts that of Britner (2008) who submitted that male have a greater sense of self-efficacy, personal control and mystery than their female counterparts. This is not in tandem with the submission of Tenaw (2013) who reported that female students have lower self-efficacy in mathematics and other science subjects when compared to male students.

The result of the study also revealed that there was no significant difference between the self-efficacy of rural and urban students exposed to the two strategies and the conventional strategy in Chemistry. However, the finding contradicted the views of other researchers who share the belief that location influences the students' self-efficacy. Dalgety and Call (2006) opined that location and environment help students to interact effectively and positively, hence enhanced self-efficacy. Owoeye and Yara (2011) and Onah (2011) in their separate studies concluded that students that were exposed to many laboratory materials and practical skills in Chemistry have better self-efficacy than their counterparts in the rural schools where these practical laboratories are absent or nearly absent.

Conclusion

The adoption of Interactive-Engagement and Analogy-Enhanced strategies helps learners to stimulate their interest in the subject, thereby leading to improved self-efficacy in Chemistry. The self-efficacy of students exposed to Interactive-Engagement, Analogy-Enhanced and conventional strategies of teaching do not differ by gender and school location. That is, the strategies are found suitable for male and female students in urban and rural schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. Chemistry teachers should embrace innovative instructional strategies by deliberate use of interactive-engagement and analogy-enhanced instructional strategies in the learning process in order to facilitate better self-efficacy in Chemistry.
2. Seminars and workshops should be organized by schools for students to promote the development of positive self-efficacy in Chemistry

References

- Adeyemo, S. A. (2012). The Relationship among School Environment, Students Approaches to Learning and their Academic Achievement in Senior Secondary School Physics. *International Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 3(1), 21 – 26.
- Aybuke, P. & Omen, G. (2012). Students' Conceptual Level of Understanding on Chemical Bonding. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(3), 563-580.

- Britner, S. L. (2008). Motivation in high school science students: A comparison of gender differences in life, physical, and earth science classes. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 45(8), 955-970.
- Britner, S. L. (2008). Motivation in high school science students: A comparison of gender differences in life, physical, and earth science classes. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 45(8), 955-970.
- Britner, S. & Pajares, F. (2006). Sources of Science Self-Efficacy Beliefs of Middle School Students. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 43(5), 485-499.
- Cahyadi, V. (2007). Improving Teaching and Learning in Introductory Physics. Ph.D Thesis, University of Canterbury, Christ church, New Zealand. *Journal of Educational Research*, 32(2), 235 – 273
- Cheung D. (2015). Secondary School Students Self-Efficacy: Measurement and Sources in *Affective Dimension in Chemistry Education* edited by M.Kahvacı and M.K. Orgill 195-215.
- Dalgety J. and Call R.K. (2006). “Exploring first year student chemistry self-efficacy: *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education* 4:97-116.
- Duniya, J.N. (2009). Comparative Laboratory Approaches and Expository Method on Acquisition of science Process Skills and Performance by Analogy Students of Polytechnics. A Proposal Seminar Paper presented to the Science Education Department ABU Zaria.
- Genden, J. (2011). What Are the Different levels of Anxiety?. Retireve March 8 2021. From <http://www.livestrong.com/article/97139-differnt-levels-anxiety/>
- Kiran, D. & Sungur, S. (2011). Middle School Students’ Science Self-Efficacy and Its Sources: Examination of Gender Difference. *Journal of Science Education Technology*, 23(3) 51-59.
- Navarro, R. & Santos, R. (2013). Assessment of Learning 2 Authentic Assessment of Students Learning Outcomes. 2nd Edition. Lorimar Publishing Inc., 776 Aurora Blvd. cor. Boston Street Cubao, Q.C., Metro Manila.
- Onah, E. F. (2011). Influence of sex and school location on students’ achievement in agricultural science. *African Journal of science, Technology and Mathematics Education (AJSTME)*, 1(1) 96-102.
- Orgil, M. K. & Thomas, M. (2007). Analogies and 5E Models. *Science Teacher*, 74(1), 40 – 45.
- Owoeye, J. S. & Yara, P. O. (2011). School location and academic achievement of secondary school in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Asian Social Science*, 7(5). www.ccsenet.org/ass.
- Pajares F. & Urdan, S.L. (2006); Sources of Science Self-Efficacy belief of middle schools students. *Journal of Research in Sciece Teaching* 43(5) 485-499.
- Samara, N. (2013). Effectiveness of Using Mind Maps as Teaching Method on Student's Achievement in Environmental Education Course at Mutah University. *Journal of Mu'tah Lil-Buhuth wad-Dirasat, Humanities and Social Sciences Series, Jordan*, 29(3), 97-124.
- Usher, E. L. & Pajares, F. (2006). Sources of academic and self-regulatory efficacy beliefs of entering middle school students. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 31, 125-141. education.uky.edu/EDP/usher

Cite this article:

Author(s), Amos Olusola OGUNJOBI (Ph.D), Stella Kemilola EKUNDAYO (Ph.D), (2021). "The Effects of Interactive-Engagement and Analogy-Enhanced Instructional Strategies On Secondary School Students' Self-Efficacy in Chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 116-128. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5072351> , Special Issue: 6, Vol.: 3, Article: 10, Month: June, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

